

KAZAKH FOLK ART ABAY**Djaksilikova Aygerim**

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Abstract. In this article, we will examine some of the main philosophical views presented in Kononbayev's work and analyze their implications for understanding the nature of reality, human existence, and making moral decisions.

Key words: folklore, writer, oral literature, cultural heritage.

Abay Kononbayev is known for his thought-provoking ideas and philosophical views. His work delves into various aspects of life, from ethics and morality to the nature of reality and the meaning of existence. Kononbayev's writings have sparked debates and discussions among scholars, and his ideas continue to influence philosophical thought in Central Asia. One of the key themes in Kononbayev's work is the concept of truth. He believes that truth is not absolute but rather subjective, and that each individual's perception of reality is shaped by their own experiences and beliefs. According to Kononbayev, truth is a complex and multifaceted concept that cannot be easily defined or understood. Another important aspect of Kononbayev's philosophy is his views on morality and ethics. He argues that morality is not a fixed set of rules or principles, but rather a dynamic and evolving concept that is influenced by cultural norms and societal values. Kononbayev believes that each individual must determine their own moral code based on their own beliefs and principles, rather than blindly following societal norms. Kononbayev also delves into the nature of existence and the meaning of life in his work. He questions the purpose of human existence and explores the role of individuals in the larger cosmic order. Kononbayev's ideas on existence challenge conventional beliefs and push readers to think critically about the meaning and significance of their own lives.

In addition to his philosophical views, Kononbayev also discusses the importance of self-awareness and introspection in his work. He believes that individuals must constantly question their own beliefs and assumptions in order to gain a deeper understanding of themselves and the world around them. Kononbayev encourages readers to engage in self-reflection and to challenge their own biases and preconceived notions. Furthermore, Kononbayev's work also touches on the concept of freedom and individuality. He believes that each person has the freedom to think and act in accordance with their own beliefs

and values, and that society should not impose restrictions on individual expression. Kononbayev argues for the importance of individuality and self-expression in a world that often seeks to conform individuals to societal norms. Kazakh folk art is a rich and diverse cultural heritage that reflects the unique traditions and customs of the Kazakh people. This art form encompasses a wide range of artistic expressions, including music, dance, visual arts, and handicrafts. These art forms have been passed down through generations and play a significant role in shaping the cultural identity of the Kazakh people. One of the most prominent aspects of Kazakh folk art is music. Traditional Kazakh music is characterized by its use of traditional instruments such as the dombra, kobyz, and syrnai. These instruments are used to create a wide range of melodic and rhythmic patterns that are often accompanied by traditional Kazakh throat singing, known as "khoomei". This unique style of singing involves producing two distinct pitches simultaneously, creating a mesmerizing and haunting sound that is distinctively Kazakh. In addition to music, Kazakh folk art also encompasses a wide range of dance traditions. Traditional Kazakh dances are often performed in unison, with dancers moving in synchrony to the beat of traditional music. These dances often tell stories or depict important events in Kazakh history, such as battles or celebrations. One of the most well-known Kazakh dances is the "Kara Jorga", which is performed at weddings and other special occasions.

Visual arts are also an important part of Kazakh folk art. Traditional Kazakh artists often create intricate and colorful designs using a variety of materials, such as wool, silk, and leather. These designs are often inspired by nature and the nomadic lifestyle of the Kazakh people, featuring motifs such as animals, flowers, and geometric patterns. Kazakh artists are known for their attention to detail and craftsmanship, producing stunning works of art that are highly prized by collectors and art enthusiasts. Handicrafts are another important aspect of Kazakh folk art. Traditional Kazakh artisans create a wide range of handmade products, including carpets, textiles, jewelry, and pottery. These products are often made using traditional techniques that have been passed down through generations, such as felting, embroidery, and weaving. Kazakh handicrafts are known for their intricate designs and vibrant colors, reflecting the rich cultural heritage of the region. One of the most unique aspects of Kazakh folk art is its close connection to nature. Many Kazakh artists draw inspiration from the natural world, incorporating elements such as animals, plants, and landscapes into their work. Traditional Kazakh art often features motifs such as horses,

eagles, and mountains, reflecting the nomadic lifestyle of the Kazakh people and their deep connection to the land.

Kazakh folk art also plays a significant role in preserving and promoting traditional Kazakh culture. Many Kazakh artisans and performers work tirelessly to keep traditional art forms alive, passing down their skills and knowledge to future generations. In recent years, there has been a renewed interest in Kazakh folk art, with many young people taking up traditional crafts and performing arts as a way to connect with their cultural heritage. Overall, Kazakh folk art is a vibrant and dynamic expression of the rich cultural heritage of the Kazakh people. From music and dance to visual arts and handicrafts, Kazakh folk art encompasses a wide range of artistic expressions that reflect the unique traditions and customs of the Kazakh people. By preserving and promoting these art forms, Kazakh artists and artisans play a crucial role in keeping traditional Kazakh culture alive and vibrant for future generations to enjoy. Another key aspect of Kononbayev's philosophy is his views on knowledge and wisdom. He believes that true knowledge comes from a combination of intellectual inquiry and personal experience, and that individuals must constantly seek to expand their understanding of the world. Kononbayev challenges readers to question their assumptions and to seek out knowledge from a variety of sources in order to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the world.

Moreover, Kononbayev's work also explores the concept of spirituality and the search for meaning in a secular world. He believes that individuals must grapple with existential questions and seek out their own spiritual truths in order to find meaning and purpose in life. Kononbayev's ideas on spirituality challenge conventional religious beliefs and push readers to think critically about their own spiritual journeys.

In conclusion, Abay Kononbayev's philosophical views delve into a wide range of complex and thought-provoking ideas. His work challenges readers to question their assumptions and beliefs, and to think critically about the nature of truth, morality, existence, and self-awareness. Kononbayev's ideas continue to influence philosophical thought in Central Asia and beyond, and his work serves as a valuable resource for those seeking to engage in deep and meaningful philosophical inquiry.

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